

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MIREMBE****FIRST NAME: DOROTHY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 13%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

Key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)

1. Starting the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7)
2. Researching the topic (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8-9)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12-19)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Styling guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40-42)

THE BENEFITS OF RESEARCH IN WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When I started this journey, I thought I would easily dive into the areas of knowledge needed in the energy sector. However, I quickly realized that I must learn how to walk before I could run. After reviewing and studying the ACA-401D course pack period one (1), it dawned on me that I must do my research and read before I start any writing. Research cannot be separated from good writing; it forms the backbone of academic and professional writing. In academic, technical, and even creative contexts, research helps writers to create informative, well-structured, and credible works that engage readers. By carefully exploring existing knowledge, research provides foundational support for arguments, enhances the writer's understanding of the subject, and helps to ensure accuracy and persuasiveness in writing. In this response paper, my discussion will address some of the main advantages of research in writing, how it has helped me develop knowledge and credibility, and activated the ability to think critically to allow a more complete writing experience as I start my doctorate journey.

a) Knowledge building

The most important thing that research does while writing is to build a person's knowledge in the area they are writing about. Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 8) urge that after understanding the topic, the next important thing is reading and researching what to write. Reading and researching will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer. When a piece of work is well-researched, it reflects deep knowledge about the topic, thus enabling me to engage in critical issues more profoundly. This is done in academic contexts by evaluating peer-reviewed articles, books, and other scholarly sources. Primary debates, theoretical perspectives, and empirical findings relevant to the topic is what research familiarizes writers with. Reading the given course pack, I was able to build knowledge and information that helped shape my writing process.

For example, in history or science, research might inform authors about previous studies or experiments and place their writing into perspective based on such a framework. Thus, when writers have access to a broad knowledge base, they can make certain arguments that are usually backed by proof and theoretical frameworks. The written work then becomes cognitively informative since the intellectual basis of the work would increase its educational value.

b) Enhance Credibility and Authority

Credibility is the key, whether in academia or a professional context. A writer, I must learn how to create trust in the readers' minds. Research plays a crucial role in establishing credibility, and a write-up devoid of sufficient evidence to support ideas and arguments is sure to look shallow or be seen as biased.

Research opens access to authoritative sources, such as peer-reviewed journals, books, or expert opinions, that increase the authority of a writer on the subject. In argumentative essays, for example, using credible data and citations from renowned sources bolsters a writer's position since it is hard to argue with their point of view. Also, referencing various studies or data from different perspectives allows a writer to provide a balanced and objective analysis, thus adding reliability to the work.

This point has been a firm reminder to avoid plagiarism when am writing as it takes away the credibility of my work, as Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 14 & 33) explain the possible penalties of plagiarism which may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course based on its severity. Because of these facts, it's imperative that I take my research seriously and ensure I give credit where it is due.

c) Fosters Critical Thinking and Analytical Skills

Research in writing is not a passive sport; it requires critical thinking. As a writer, I must engage with the sources critically, and this is supported by (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14), who states that "One strategy for taking a view seriously is to "argue against

yourself” when you make a criticism: ask yourself how the philosopher you are criticizing would respond to your criticism”. This means that I must analyse my sources critically, verifying their quality and relevance of information.

The synthesis of information from various sources develops writers' own analytical competencies. Such a process entails the comparing of divergent points of view, the identification of patterns, and the creation of logical arguments that are susceptible to empirical verification. Writing developed out of critical research is bound to make more reasonable arguments with fresh ideas and perspectives. That is what gives the depth required for writing to be considered superior and not superficial.

For example, if I were to write about global climate change, as a researcher, I would have to obtain data not only from scientific sources but also critically assess the points of view standing in conflict about the reason and way out. Therefore, I should be able to handle complex problems and present an all-around analysis. Critical research, hence, provides me with a better opportunity to stand up for specific controversial issues, where their arguments are not unfounded.

d) Encourages Creativity and Innovation

“Do not make writing boring and clumsy” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2012, 13), while research is often associated with fact-based and technical writing, it can also be a stimulus for creativity. During my study of ACA-401D course pack period one (1), am challenged to explore the wide array of perspectives different from the ones I knew, and even better, I am exposed to fosters new ideas and linkages that perhaps would not have been obvious to the me at the start of the course. I can comfortably urge that good research does not lock any writer into a repetition of what already exists; rather, it gives her raw materials for original thought and creativity.

As I started preparing for my 1st response paper, I drew my inspiration from the detailed course pack from both the videos and text to creatively inform my writing based on the research facts made by Cleenwereck & Gulma 2021 to garner believability and substance in my paper that can enable any reader to relate much better. Moreover, reading this course pack encouraged my innovation because it provided me with the potential to question norms of thought and develop new solutions and theories, and I believe that it is through this critical combination of rigorous research and creative thinking that true intellectual and creative progress takes place among disciplines.

2) CONCLUSION

For someone who wanted to run before I could walk, I was humbly reminded that baby steps are the best for not only stable development but also to create a strong foundation for my academic journey. The ACA-401D period (1) course pack was very elaborate and enabled me to hone my research skills to be able to creatively deliver this response paper (RP1). The research and reading have helped me develop thoughts that are

cognizant, persuasive, innovative, and intellectually sound, making me multidimensional and trying to reach a potential beyond mere gathering of information. The journey has been very educative, and indeed, anyone who stops learning is old. I look forward to seeing how this journey unfolds at each step as I work towards being a problem solver.

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